

Nationality & Networks: Reflections on the historiography of photomechanical printing, Joseph Berres's work in particular¹

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Looking into a rather narrow circle of material and people associated with the origins of photomechanical printing, this paper aims to point out two fairly general phenomena and their limits, or their potential which we regularly come across, both in the study of period sources and the reading of later publications. The first case regards the historiography of the earliest era of photomechanical printing, which has been nationally tinged and hierarchizing since its birth. The narrative is frequently dominated by efforts to decide who is the winner – to say which inventor was really the “first”, or the “first truly successful” one, which process was the best, etc. The second phenomenon which will be stressed, seldom emerges in the discourse, although it was actually of key importance for the first achievements in the development of photomechanical printing methods – it is the networks of relations which formed the base for the development and distribution of the first photomechanical prints and technologies. I do not mean to argue that hierarchizing or a canon based on several prominent figures are inherently bad or dysfunctional. However, I am certain that their presence and influence should be taken into account and that it is necessary to duly interpret the limits stemming from them.

1/

Many stories about the beginnings of the “photo–ink relationship” start with the question as to what motivated the first inventors. The usual answer is two-folded: on the one hand, there was the uniqueness (“the one-and-only existence”) of each daguerreotype, on the other hand the instability of the early calotypes. Nonetheless, if we talk about the first purely experimental phase, i.e. approximately about the period between August 1839 and the years 1841/1842 when the wider specialist public acknowledged the success of the French physicist Hippolyte Fizeau (1819–1896), the first holds true. And as a matter of fact the majority of known experiments with photomechanical printing in the early 1840s involved the daguerreotype plate.

In my opinion, the idea of a daguerreotype as a mere semi-finished product, or a base for a print matrix, was logical and followed from the general experience with the metal, particularly copper plate bearing an image. It is no coincidence that the idea to print from daguerreotypes was embraced by a number of contemporaries. Some of those who allegedly immediately realised the potential of daguerreotype as the base for print matrices did not go beyond the idea, others tried but only a handful of them were truly determined and succeeded to a varying extent, be it with the use of chemical or electro-chemical process of etching. For that matter, attempts – though not very successful and with different aims – were even made by Daguerre himself. The fact that the idea of printing from a daguerreotype plate – or “facilitating its adaptation to useful purposes” was nothing unique is also testified by an article published in *The Athenaeum* on 12 October 1839. And it was not just a happy coincidence that the author stressed also the potential of another very fresh method of

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reproduction with regard to photomechanical printing – the galvanoplasty or electrotyping invented by Moritz H. Jacobi (1801–1874). I will refer to his invention later on.

There were three canonical pioneers of printing from daguerreotypes. The first one was the French physician Alfred Donné (1801–1878), who was credited with the first successful attempts to print from etched daguerreotype plates, despite the fact that their success had been highly disputable from the start. The second was Joseph Berres (1796–1844), a professor of anatomy at Vienna University, whose method – called *Phototyp* (hereafter as phototyp) – was based on multiple etching by nitric acid, later combined with galvanising and electrotyping. The third member of the canon is the mentioned Hippolyt Fizeau. His method, much more complex, but again combining chemical and electrolytic treatments, was in 1842, like Berres's phototyp earlier, awarded the medal of the Society for the Encouragement of Industry in Paris. Some of his supporters described the process as by far the most successful and unparalleled as late as in the 1850s. Other pioneers such as William Robert Grove (1811–1896), Antoine Claudet (1797–1867), Karl Hammerschmidt (1801–1874), etc. are usually only mentioned after this trio, with varying frequency. Some of these names are well-known today, though from different contexts, others fell into oblivion shortly after publishing.

The delusion concerning the gradual perfecting of photomechanical printing, or a linear succession of people and processes which in fact often cannot be clearly distinguished from one another, is not a product of 20th-century historiography. The origins of this slow march can be traced in period criticism. What is important, however, is that it was then that several parallel, highly autonomous narratives started to take shape in different parts of Europe and in the USA, and their intersections are more or less negligible. Possibly the strongest position was occupied by the concept introduced by French historiography and based on French production. One reason might be the relatively great interest on the part of historians, another reason might be the objectively better starting position for the development of photomechanical printing in the early 1840s: I mean the availability of high-quality daguerreotypes one could experiment with. While the situation of the English and Welsh was considerably complicated by Daguerre's patent, daguerreotypists and printers in Vienna had to cope with a lack of quality raw material – metal plates, the manufacture of which in Austria seriously lagged behind.

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In the next part of my paper I am going to focus on Joseph Berres's contribution to the beginnings of photomechanical printing, as his example – despite the relatively limited material evidence – enables to observe a number of important aspects of the history of photomechanical printing: its technological development, social context, historiography and theoretical reflections. This approach is underpinned by two important circumstances. Firstly, the time and space delineating Berres's experiments was relatively narrow, the reason being his untimely death at the end of 1844 and the fact that compared to London or Paris, Vienna was rather small, half their size, and the local photographic scene was much more compact and today more transparent. Secondly, and necessarily, Berres only devoted himself to the development of photomechanical printing briefly, yet intensively, and what is more, in a city where photography flourished like hardly anywhere else. In Vienna, a relatively large group of people, centred around Andreas Ettingshausen (1796–1878) and Carl Schuh (1806–1863), took up photography almost overnight; the circle was known as *Fürstenhofrunde*. The members of this informal association pursued not only the daguerreotype, but also – and this is crucial – the further perfection of photographic technologies, such as the development of more sensitive emulsions, optics, cameras, lighting, raw materials and related fields,

electrotyping in particular. This constellation and concentration was truly unique, and substantially contributed to the rapid development of the daguerreotype process in the first two years.

As an anatomist, Berres had intensively pursued microscopy from the 1820s, first during his engagement at Francis University in Lviv and later at Vienna University, where he started to teach pathology and anatomy in 1831. His scientific work and interest in microscopy culminated in the publication [Anatomie der mikroskopischen Gebilde des menschlichen Körpers](#) (1837) which contained, apart from Latin and German texts, also a number of full-page copper engraving illustrations made on the basis of careful microscopic observations. The publication brought Berres recognition and public acclaim, and it became groundwork for his future efforts in the development of a more simple manner of the mechanical reproduction of scientific images, especially microscopic. It is hardly surprising that in Vienna it was Berres that became not only the pioneer of the daguerreotype photomicrograph (together with Andreas Ettingshausen and Carl Schuh), but also of photomechanical printing.

According to his own words, Berres started to implement his vision of the mechanically reproduced microscopic image which could be employed in practical science on 1 April 1840, a month after he had succeeded in creating the first daguerreotype photomicrograph with the use of the hydro-oxygen microscope. And “*as luck would have it, I made my first etching [with nitric acid] as early as on 5 April*”² – i.e. in only five days; it was no coincidence that it regarded a microscopic image. In the weeks and months to follow, he continued to carry out multiple experiments, and he would regularly present the results to his colleagues and the Vienna public, through articles in the press as well as public presentations; the first one took place on 30 April at a meeting of the Society of Viennese Physicians. It involved the reproduction of a print with the image of [a girl with a butterfly](#). It was swiftly followed by further prints, and not only reproductions of copperplate engravings, like [Amor carving a bow](#), a portrait of Emperor Francis, [Judith and Holofernes](#), a Venetian scene called [Venedig wie es war](#) – but also several views of Vienna, for example, [Ferdinand Bridge](#), [Josephsplatz](#) or a view of [St. Stephen’s Cathedral](#), taken from the observatory of the old university. The majority of motifs mentioned in the period press are known from preserved incunabula; some copies preserved for example in New York Public Library, Albertina, Moravian Gallery, Wien Museum, Rijksmuseum and some more. Unfortunately, there are no portraits or photomicrographs.

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Berres’s first experiments are relatively easy to map thanks to the number of texts which he and his colleagues regularly published in the Austrian and international press. It is thus known that the method he referred to as phototyp was not a one-off but that he continuously improved the original procedure, experimented with different concentrations of nitric acid, the etching time, repeated etching, combined etching with electrolysis, aquatint, and with the help from a graphic artist sometimes even retouching and manual interventions in the image. This is obvious both from prints and matrices. In July 1841, for example, the professor of the Prague Polytechnic Ferdinand Hessler (1803–1865) wrote about three methods developed and applied by Berres, allegedly with the use of pure silver daguerreotype plates. This multidisciplinary approach naturally required collaboration with specialists, and not only graphic artists and printers – like Josef Axmann (1793–1873) – but also experts in other disciplines, some of them from the *Fürstenhofrunde* circle. With many prints it is virtually impossible to determine the creator’s share; similarly, it is difficult to define a chronological

² Joseph Berres, ‘Fixation und Druck von Daguerre’s Lichtbildern,’ *Beilage zur Allgemeine Zeitung* (Augsburg), 18 August 1840, no. 231, p. 1833 (1833–1834).

sequence, despite the fact that many of them feature authentic technical notes – about the period of origin, order, and partially also about the technology.

A special role in this respect was played by the pioneers of the electrotyping in Vienna – Erwin Waidele and Franz Theyer (1809–1871); the best evidence of this collaboration is the preserved [electrotype copy plate](#) and prints with the motif from [Venice](#). The daguerreotype and only a few months older galvanoplasty thus profited from the mutual synergy, and both were often pioneered by the same people; for example in Vienna also by Carl Schuh, the owner of the first portrait photographic studio, and in Munich by Franz Kobell (1803–1882). This close relationship had already been signalled by the first texts announcing the invention of the daguerreotype in 1839. In this regard, electrotyping should be seen as an integral part of the history of photography.

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Berres tried to actively promote his invention especially in the first two years, as not only a functioning technology but even as the most perfect one. As the evidence of his achievements and the result of his experiments, he sent specimens to several European academies (e.g. Russian Academy, Academia Galileiana), numerous prominent scientific societies (e.g. Royal Polytechnic Institution), the Vienna court (Emperor Ferdinand I, Archduke Ludwig), high state officials, including the Chancellor Metternich, editorial boards of influential periodicals (e.g. *The Athenaeum*), as well as to many leading scientific authorities, including W.H.F. Talbot and Alexander Humboldt. And he also included his first major rival Alfred Donné who, however, did not hesitate to strike back. Some of the recipients were sent individual prints, others – like Humboldt – received a series in the form of a publication entitled [Phototyp nach der Erfindung des Professor Berres in Wien](#) which contained, apart from several examples, also an accompanying commentary on the method and its application.

As I have mentioned earlier, few Berres's original phototyps are known today, only about forty altogether, despite the fact that according to period reports it was possible to make several hundred prints from each plate, and when combined with the galvanoplasty even a countless number (theoretically). All the mentioned contacts provide clues to others, both in private property and institutions; for example, three specimens were recently discovered among a set of plates, prints and electrotypes from the estate of Franz Theyer. Another fresh clue leads to the Academia Galileiana in Padua. In this case, no phototyp has been found yet, but there is a written record thanks to which the names of other people among Berres's colleagues active in the field of photomechanical prints, involved directly in the development, practice or distribution and promotion of Berres's invention, have come to light.

5/

I would like to comment briefly on the period criticism. It is obvious from newspaper reports, manuals and correspondence that the key instrument in the search for and determination of “the most perfect” photomechanical process was the magnifying glass. It was used to assess the two main criteria, the richness of tonality and the refinement of grain or raster, and it could also reveal whether there had been any manual interventions in the image or whether it had originated “a la prima” – as a genuine photomechanical print.

Leaving aside that assessments rooted in visual perception were bound to be subjective, a number of critics did not hesitate to evaluate the individual processes based on one or two specimens. Yet even with small series such as Berres's one it is obvious how technically varied they are. In addition,

many commentaries and assessments echoed nationalist, institutional and geographical affinities and animosities.

Not even Berres did refrain from making comments, often directed at his French colleagues who – in his eyes – ignored inventions originating from Vienna: “When one follows reports on heliography in public journals one is surprised how little attention is paid to what has been delivered to the public, or how much is declined only to get a chance to make a discovery of something that has been already discovered.”³ It should be noted that until the early 1850s none of the processes reached such overall quality that it could be actually marketed.

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This brings me to the end, or back to the two aspects mentioned in the introduction. A great part of the period discourse of the 1840s and the early 1850s, including qualitative assessments of the individual technologies, appear to have transformed into modern historiography. The result is several parallel one-sided narratives which differ not just in details but often substantially.

But as I’ve mentioned, roots of this need to be looked for in the 19th century. For example, in 1848, in a report to the Society for the Encouragement of Industry in Paris Armand Pierre de Seguier (1803–1876) stated: “I have to say that the major breakthrough in chemical engraving of photomechanical printing was achieved by Dr. Donné, who was followed by Mr Choiselat and Mr Ratel. The deceased Berres in Vienna kept up with them. But one has to acknowledge that Mr Fizeau who came thereafter achieved a target unreachable to anybody before.”⁴ Quite an opposite idea presented in 1857 Anton Perger (1809–1876) – a copyist of the Royal library in Vienna and also a photomechanical printing enthusiast – to members of the Viennese Academy of Sciences: “reproducing of photographs by means of copperplate printing is in fact an Austrian thing.”⁵

It is as if the two worlds were completely separate, although the development of photomechanical printing, especially at the onset, was an international and collaborative affair, and an important part was played not only by inventors but also by a whole network of other individuals and institutions involved, for example, in distribution, promotion and criticism. We have to take into account not only the fact that the term phototyp covered a range of processes or variants, but also the input from his collaborators, collectors, competitors, links to institutions – in Austria and abroad, science authorities, colleagues, publishers, editors, supporters of all kinds, family etc.

Thus, if we really want to learn more about the beginnings of photomechanical printing, we should bear in mind the presence, or the absence, of both phenomena: on the one hand nationalization which pervades the present and past historiography of photomechanical printing, in other words, the existence of further parallel narratives, and on the other hand the network of personal, institutional, historical, social and cultural links without which the origins of photomechanical printing would remain just a list of names and an artificial, meaningless chronology.

³ Joseph Berres, ‘Die Daguerreotypie in Wien,’ *Wiener Zeitung*, 24 June 1841, no. 172, p. 1302 (1301–1302).

⁴ Seguier [Armand Pierre Séguier], ‘Rapport sur le concours pour le perfectionnement de la photographie,’ *Bulletin de la Société d’encouragement pour l’industrie nationale* 1848, 47, no. 526 (April), p. 197 (195–200).

⁵ Anton von Perger, ‘Über die Vervielfältigung von Lichtbildern (Photographien) durch Ätzungen und Galvanoplastik,’ *Sitzungsberichte der Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftlichen Classe der Kais. Akademie d. Wissenschaften* 1857, p. 76 (76–77).